

CHALLENGES FACED BY NOVICE TEACHERS IN THEIR FIRST YEAR OF TEACHING

Jorayeva Muxlisa Zokir qizi
Qobiljonova Iroda Olimjon qizi
jorayevamuxlisa768@gmail.com
Irodakabilzanova@gmail.com

Students of Uzbekistan State World Languages University
Scientific supervisor: **Masharipov Yunus Akhmed ugli**
ESL teacher of Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Abstract. First year of teaching is broadly recognized as one of the most critical and professionally challenging years in a teachers' career. Per-service training and the complex reality of the classroom often faced by novice teachers, lead to experiences described in the literature as "reality shock" and "transition shock". This research examines challenges faced by beginning teachers during their first year of professional practice, such as classroom management difficulties, excessive workload, lack of institutional support, and the disconnect between theoretical preparation and real school environments. The study relies on qualitative data from semi-structure survey interviews with novice teachers, aged 20-25 who study, work and live in Uzbekistan, as well as findings from international studies carried in Turkey, Vietnam, and Qatar. The research contains three core interview questions guided the data collection: challenges and their effects on confidence, strategies of classroom management and workload, and the nature of institutional support received. The findings foster the urgent need for structured mentoring programs, more practice-oriented per-service preparation, reduced administrative burdens on first-year teachers and reveal common patterns across diverse contexts. The study offers practical and effective recommendations for educational institutions and policymakers.

Key words: novice teachers, first year of teaching, classroom management, teacher support, mentoring, professional challenges, teacher retention, induction programs.

Introduction

The inflection from teachers' education theories into actual classroom practice is one of the most unmanageable processes for any educators. In spite of academic preparation, most of new educators enter their first classroom with feeling unprepared, isolated and overwhelmed. Researchers have long described this process using vivid metaphors: Corcoran (1981) spoke about "transition shock", while Fantilli and McDougall (2009) describe it as a "survive and thrive" or even "sink or swim" encounter. This data illustrates a universal reality where beginning teachers are generally counted as those in their first five year comfort occupation difficulties that higher education programs routinely fail to anticipate.

The consequences of this challenging induction period are crucial. Studies highlights that 25% to 50% of new teachers abandon within five years. (Bang at al 2007; Massengill et al., 2005). Such high attrition squanders institutional investments and compromises student learning outcomes, positioning the analysis of early-career challenges as an urgent policy imperative.

This research demonstrates three main areas of teachers first year. Firstly, it is concerns personal and professional challenges and their influence on confidence and teaching quality. Secondly, it focuses on practicality such as classroom management, lesson planning, and time

allocation. Lastly evaluates systemic support structures including mentorship and administrative aid, during the induction phase. These three areas served as foundation for a qualitative survey of new teachers, combined with a global research review.

Methodology

This study operates a qualitative research design gathering primary data collection within structured survey interviews with a comparative review of international academic literature. The key information were combined through responses to three open-ended interview questions administrated to beginning teachers in their first years of professional practice. The questions were designed to get subjective experiences and perceptions across three core themes: difficulties and their impact on confidence, classroom and workload management strategies, and institutional support received.

Survey Interview Questions:

- What were the biggest challenges you experienced during your first year of teaching, and how did they affect your confidence and performance?
- How did you manage classroom behavior, lesson planning, and workload during your first year, and what difficulties did you face in these areas?
- What kind of support (e.g., mentoring, training, administration) did you receive in your first year and what additional support do you think would have helped you more?

The answers were sported out employing thematic content analysis to identify recurring patterns and categories. The primary data were then compared with findings from three international studies: a multiple-case qualitative study conducted in Turkey with three beginning teachers using semi-structured interviews and observations over one full school year (Engunay & Adiguzel, 2019); a qualitative interview study with six novice university lecturers in Hanoi, Vietnam, exploring research-related working conditions (Lan, 2022); and semi-structured interview study with 15 novice teachers in Qatar government school using thematic bottom-up analytical approach (Al-Naimi et al., 2020). This multi-source approach allowed for both contextual specificity and cross-cultural generalizability in the findings.

Discussion

Personal and professional challenges and their impact on confidence.

Survey results clearly illustrates that the first year of teaching is a time intensive personal stress and self-doubt .The primary source of this issue is discrepancy between theoretical preparation and the university level and the multi- faced reality of actual school environment .Many participants described felling overwhelmed by responsibilities they had not anticipated, from managing students behavior regulation to bureaucratic demands. This is classic “reality shock” phenomenon, well established in the literature, was confirmed across all study contexts.

In the Turkish context, a cross-case analysis identified personal and professional growth as a primary domain of difficulty alongside classroom management and organization process (Ergunay & Adiguzel 2019). Similarly in Qatar, several new teachers shared with their work experience and feelings .They feel incompetent and helpless during their first months. Some even described feelings of depression and panic caused by warnings from school administration and unpredictable demands (AL-Naimi et al., 2020). The participants in our survey backed up these findings. They noted that losing confidence directly stopped them from trying new teaching methods and from keeping their students focused during the lesson.

Both survey data and international research underscore that this initial phase is a critical juncture where new teachers either solidify their professional identity or begin to disengage .Teachers who received even minimal encouragement from experienced colleagues during

this period reported recovering more quickly , underscoring the role of collegial relationship in sustaining first-year teachers .

Classroom Management, Lesson Planning, and Workload

Classroom management remains the most pervasive obstacle cited across the datasets. Surveyed educators struggled to maintain student focus, handle disruptive incidents, and assert authority without alienating their classes. This closely correlates with Qatari study where two-thirds of the cohort identified classroom discipline such as students ignoring instructions and peer conflict during the lessons the major barrier , noting a specific lack of practical strategies to solve this problem (AL-Nami et al .,2020).

The lesson planning constituted a distinct professional challenge characterized by a disproportionate time investment compared to their experienced peers , often lacking proper mentoring ,templates ,or curriculum familiarity .In Qatar ,some educators showed frustration with standardized plans that stopped them from adapting creatively ,while others believed they received too little direction on how to adjust teaching for students at different academic levels. Lesson planning is not just technical task but source of job-related anxiety.

Workload stood is another major issue survey participants reported that the high number of tasks given to them in their first year such as teaching ,administrative work , student supervision , and mandatory professional development left very little time to reflect , prepare or recover .In Qatar some beginner teachers had to teach twelve periods a weak in their first year with classes of 33to 40students ,which one teacher said made individual instruction almost impossible (Al-Naimi et al .,2020).Meanwhile ,in Vietnam, beginning lectures stated that they had to take extra jobs outside the university to support themselves financially , reducing their time for professional duties even more (Lan,2022).This pattern of structural overload is a common feature that new teachers experience in many different countries.

Institutional support: What was received and what was needed.

Survey responds stated that they received limited and often poor support from their institutions in their first year. The most common types of support were official induction meetings and occasional observations by managers, which teachers usually found insufficient for solving daily classroom problems. While informal help for coworkers was called useful more often, getting this help was inconsistent and depended on a teacher's own effort.

A study from Vietnam highlights the gap between what schools give and what new teachers actually need. Six new college new teachers were happy to get research paper and information about conferences. But expressed strong dissatisfaction with the absence of mentor materials, limited financial resources for professional activities, and excessive research hour requirements that functioned more as institutional pressure than genuine professional encouragement (Lan., 2022). One of teacher described felling like she was "swimming in the sea on my own" a phrase that captures the experience of format support that does not translate into practical guidance.

In Qatar, teachers coped by talking to administrators and experienced peers, using online tools for self- directed learning, and sometimes moving to another schools or quitting teaching completely (AL-Naimi et al., 2020). Similarly, the Turkish study suggested that teachers education programs should include more practice hours and make practicum experience more demanding and realistic (Ergunay&Adiguzel,2019).Finally ,participants in the present study clearly asked for structured mentoring from experienced staff , less paperwork at the start , and training that solves real classroom problems instead of repeating university lessons.

Conclusion

Novice teachers experience significant challenges across diverse national and institutional contexts during their first year of teaching period. This study shows that the difficulties faced by new teachers are not isolated or context-specific but reflect structural patterns inherent to how educational systems get and integrate new professionals, generating both primary survey data and comparative international literature.

Main source of difficulties embrace classroom management, workload, lesson planning and theory-practice. Simultaneously, another common finding is that the support provided by institutions is often not very effective because it is too broad, happens too rarely, or does not match the real challenges that teachers face during their first year of teaching. According to both surveys, the need of novice teachers organized induction programs that extend across the full first year, customized mentoring from professional colleagues and recognition that beginning teachers require time, guidance, and reduced non-teaching burdens in order to develop.

The high number of teachers leaving the profession is not unavoidable. In many cases, it happens because educational institutions fail to give new teachers enough support during an important stage of their professional growth. To improve teacher retention and performance in the long term, schools need to invest seriously in induction programs- not simply as a formal requirement for the teacher who will educate future generations.

Reference

1. Ergünay, O., & Adıgüzel, O. C. (2019). The challenges of beginning teachers in their first year of teaching career and their sources. *Journal of Qualitative Research in Education*, 7(3). <https://doi.org/10.14689/issn.2148-624.1.7c.3s.8m>
2. Lan, L. T. (2022). Difficulties facing novice teacher-researchers in terms of working conditions and the support they need. *VNU Journal of Foreign Studies*, 38(3), 52–68. <https://js.vnu.edu.vn/FS/article/view/4842/4303>
3. AL-Naimi, S. R., Romanowski, M. H., & Du, X. (2020). Novice teachers' challenges and coping strategies in Qatari government schools. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 19(9), 118–142. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.19.9.7>